

VERBS WITH THE MEANING OF ACTION IN THE UZBEKI LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article discusses the emergence of spiritual groups in Uzbek linguistics, the scientific and methodological functions of action verbs.

Key words: Uzbek language, verb, word group, semantics, verbs of action, verbs of state.

The theory of semantic fields entered Uzbek linguistics after the 1970s. The study of words as a semantic field began mainly with the articles of M. Sodikova. In his articles, the semantic field of adjectives with an archiseme denoting scope is researched, and thus they were explained.

In this way, studies using the CT method also began to appear in Uzbek semasiology. Prof. I. Kochkourtouev was one of the first in Uzbek to write a special article about the convenience of the CT method in researching the lexical system. showed the need to use the CT method in solving the most important tasks of Uzbek semasiology, such as determining the place of each sememe in the general dictionary system.

The linguist J. Ismoilov also used CT method to determine their semantic structure mainly in the process of researching personal nouns.

In 1978 Sh.Rakhmatullaev, developing his thoughts about the CT method, published the article "From the experience of component analysis of lexical meaning" ("Uzbek language and literature", 1978, issue 4, pp. 56-60).

In M. Narziueva's researches, the meaning structure of nouns describing a person in terms of age was studied. His article published in 1986 analyzed the use of simple (root) blood-relative terms only in their meaning [II.14]. Of course, the article widely used the traditions of component analysis of kinship terms of European and Russian linguistics. His candidate's thesis consists of 3 chapters, in chapter 1 there is a small group of nouns describing a person in terms of "pure age" and its structure, in chapter 2 the lexical composition and internal description of nouns of kinship - in chapter 3, in chapter 3 there is a description of nouns describing a person in terms of age. figurative meanings are interpreted. It seems that M. Narziueva checked the use of nouns in their own and figurative meanings.

The research of R. Rasulov was of great importance in the study of the verb semantic groups of the Uzbek system lexicology, in checking their inter-system

relations, semantic richness. In his monograph (1989), the basics of the substantive approach to the word were developed, and an example of CT of verbs was shown. So, the vocabulary (lexicon) of the language, including the group of active verbs, is a unique system.

About action verbs.

In recent years, attention is being paid to the semantic analysis of word groups. In Uzbek linguistics, the semantic features of verbs, classification issues are in the focus of attention of linguists. In this respect, the works of A. Hojiyev, I. Kochkortoyev, K. Kholikov, M. Sodikova, R. Rasulov and many researchers can be counted. For example, K. Kholikov distinguished several spiritual groups of verbs: "There are still a number of verb classes that belong to scientific research, as well as the lexical-semantic classification of verbs, their specific grammatical features need to be thoroughly studied." the idea was raised [II.37]. R. Rasulov's research work in this field is noteworthy. Case verbs and their LMGs have been deeply studied and analyzed by the scientist. The internal appearance of state verbs (such as continuous state, performance state, biological state, physiological state, mental state verbs) is separated.

LMGs of verbs in Turkic languages were first determined by N.K. Dmitriyev: verbs of speech, verbs of perception, verbs of activity, action. This classification is still used in practice. Because there is this division in the 6th grade "Mother Language" textbook. Determining the LMGs of verbs, in-depth study of each group is the object of separate scientific works and requires special research. A.A. Salkalamanidze, while studying the lexical-semantic groups of verbs, groups them based on verb valence, and defines verb valence on their transitive and intransitive [30, 18-19].

The meanings of verbs are divided into a number of substantive groups, in which creation, breaking, changing, speaking, sensing, directing are characteristic of actions; psychological, economic, psychological aspects specific to the situation are taken into account.

I. Verbs of action express the activity characteristic of humans, animals, and inanimate objects. They are related to walking, touching, and striking.

Moving objects are clearly visible in movements related to hands, face, mouth, body. For example:

1. Verbs related to leg movements. This action is mainly given by the verb "to walk". Related to walking:

a) walk - Lali walks with Boronbek (H. Gulom);

b) to sneer - The boy fell in front of his mother and sneered (Oybek);

- d) to run - The children ran to the playground;
- e) to get up - You will drink the tea yourself later, - he said to Ayshabonu (H.G.), who was getting up from his seat.
- f) to stagger - He staggered and looked at the beautiful eyes of Ghulamjon (M. Ism.);
- g) to store - Soli went out until it was cold (M. Ism.);
- h) to crawl - Arif brother suddenly dragged his leg, which had become numb (A.M.);
- i) click one by one - Aunt Jannat got up, looked out of the street door by clicking one by one (S.Ahmad);
- j) to prowl - The thug is prowling somewhere until dawn (A.Q.);
- k) to be reined in - the horse was startled by the snake that came out in front of Behos and was reined back a little (H.G.);
- l) to crawl - A cart crawled like a spider from the horizon (A.Q.).

Actions such as kicking, kicking, stomping, and stomping are performed with the feet. There are also colorful realizations of the verb "to walk" related to the meaning of movement (such as Stanok walked; the clock walked; the train walked).

2. Verbs related to hand movements include:

- a) to catch and its figurative meanings:
to catch a pen, to catch a thief, to be caught at work, etc.
- b) stroking-My father strokes the heads of the orphans;
- d) scratch - The cat scratched the child's hand;
- e) to slap - he slapped Sherali's face (M. Noun);
- f) to pinch - Nadirmohbegim stretched out his foot from inside the sandal and pinched Unsin's calf (A.Q.);
- g) massage-The boy massaged his grandmother's feet;
- h) to tickle-Girls tickled each other and laughed;
- i) grab - The eagle grabbed its prey and rose to the sky;
- j) to fight - Two boys who were talking in the middle suddenly started fighting (H.G.);
- k) click - The teacher clicked the table (P. Kadirov.);
- l) to take a handful - Sidiqjon took a handful of raisins and put them in his mouth (A.Q.);
- m) to clap-They clapped (A.Q.);
- n) to shake hands - He shook his hand.

There are also action verbs related to facial, body, and mouth movements.

II. Speech verbs are related to the act of speaking. Such verbs are related to human activity.

a) to speak (synonyms - to speak, to say, to say) ☑ He himself noticed that Elchibek began to speak more lively (A.Mukh.);

b) to sneeze - Oh, don't sneeze! (H.G.);

d) grumbling - He grumbled with the sound of a young man (A.Q.);

e) to mutter (to mumble) The woman mumbled something (A.Q).

There are also variants of these verbs with a negative character: vaisamak, valdiramak, vakillamak, zhavalamak, etc. There are themes of gossiping and talking too much. The analytical form of these speech verbs is also found:

He told me

did not answer

babbled.

III. State verbs. Physical, expressive mental states characteristic of human nature have their own character. We can divide the cases into four:

a) internal state (related to mental experiences);

b) external state (related to happiness, anger);

d) physical condition (related to health, illness, strength, weakness);

e) social status (verbs related to wealth, poverty).

Verbs of mental and psychological state are mainly characteristic of a person and are related to thoughts, memories, forgetting, pain, bitterness, burning. These are mainly given by static and phraseological expressions, and also these verbs are related to brain (thought, thought), heart (heart), and the same words zi is also sometimes involved in speech. Such verbs are given as thinking verbs in new programs and textbooks (for schools):

To be absorbed in thought ~ to immerse oneself in thought

Thinking - not being able to think

Imagination escape

Remember to remember

Bring to mind

To be sad

to remember

to forget

To take heart.

These are often related to the inner spiritual world of a person. The following can be added to the verbs of the situation related to the external situation:

to be confused

To lose consciousness

To freeze

Dress up

to hold

Get nervous

To be proud

To be happy.

More figurative meaning is expressed in the verbs "to be angry" and "to be angry". There are also intensifying forms of the verbs of this case:

hit

To carry inside.

There are also expressions that express verbs of state:

A dog scratches inside

Even if they put a light in it, it won't light up

Dili became a prayer and others.

A person's external, objective influence, life difficulties or illness, physical pain, suffering can be expressed with various verbs, verb combinations, and phraseology:

To bear the pain (to bear the pain of separation)

To suffer ~ to suffer ~ to suffer

To get involved

Squatting

To crush the liver ~ to crush the heart

To draw bitter juice, etc.

Social status verbs include verbs related to economic changes in people's lives: to become rich, to become poor...

Resultant action verbs such as to make, to build, to create, to form, to draw, to write, to build, to saw, to break, to polish, to cut, to break, to eat, to delete, and to think, to fantasize, There are also verbs of thinking, such as to judge, to think, to bring to mind. These are simple and combined.

Scientist M. Sodikova, who studied verb stylistics, gives relational verbs and divides them into groups:

1. Positive attitude verbs;
2. Verbs of negative attitude.

In the first group, he included such things as to caress, deceive, love, be charmed, tame, sidestep, get in the middle, feel sorry for, flatter, enjoy, and be a butterfly. At first glance, these are similar to case verbs. But in the context (text)

he discovers a unique stylistic feature: He misses his children, caresses them from morning till night. The second group includes such things as let it be good, let it be worse, let God take it, let it be black, let it stay in order, be in trouble, and let it be young. In such verbs, most of the time, the forms "sin" and "gur" are found. This group of verbs is characterized by the verbs associated with fighting, jerking, and pushing. Methodical and phonetic features of relational verbs are a source of research to be studied separately.

In conclusion, it can be said that there are many verbs in speech. Their form of use, construction aspects are different. It should also be noted that case verbs in the Uzbek language have been studied in depth and in detail. Case verbs and their lexical-semantic groups were determined in the work of R. Rasulov. The nature of transitivity and intransitivity of state verbs in the Turkish language is deeply analyzed. According to the objective basis, verbs of active action in the language include actions - processes in nature and society, in the animal world. That is, verbs of action differ from verb lexemes belonging to other semantic fields by their breadth and complexity, variety, and expression of different actions specific to matter, permanence, according to their material basis (object). Since the reality, objectivity of the movement is related to its implementation by a certain living being, its "materialization" in it, the existence of a logical subject is measured by its absolute movement. More precisely, movement is the living form of matter.

The semantic field of verbs is formed based on the "active action" schema of the verbs of action.

The unifying sema is initially part of the common sema and is separated as a result of the analysis. When one is compared to the other, the generality of common meaning of action verbs is wide, and it is considered an important theme specific to action verbs within languages. The unifying sema is similar to the common sema, but it is a sema that always occurs after the common sema, is determined, and narrows the scope of the expression of the common sema. So, one or another LSG of action verbs is formed based on the unifying theme.

It is known that any generality arises from particularity, individuality, their logical internal connection and is manifested through particularity depending on the situation. So, the movement is seen as a generality, and they have relative independence and individuality. Movement is a theme that ensures the independence of verbs with a common theme and causes them to be interpreted as a language and speech unit. It is considered the main, central theme, and it harmonizes other important and insignificant themes around it in

the speech. They are kept as a possibility ready to emerge in a particular speech situation.

